

Socio Economic Conditions of the Interstate Migrant workers in Kozhikode District of Kerala

ALKA SHAJU

ABSTRACT

Migration is a global phenomenon revealing the nature of the people in search of better life and living condition caused by economic, social, political, cultural, environmental, health and educational factors, affecting both the origin and destination. The Migrant workers. According to International Labor organization Convention no.189 and International Organization for migration, any persons “moving to another country or region to better their material or social conditions and improve the prospect for themselves or their family.” According to the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs/Population Division (2013) International Migration Report, 232 million people live outside their countries of birth. In the coming decades, demographic forces, globalization, and climate changes will increase migration pressures both within and across borders. (Saif Muhammed, 2014). In India labor is migratory in character in all the aspects, which is the dynamic factor in the dismal scenario of Kerala in the present period. The migration of labor occupies greater significance in the Indian economy, which a thought emerged from unequal development where the people from ‘backward region’ moved to ‘developed regions’

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Migration has been a significant catalyst in Kerala state's economy. With a diminishing diaspora of the size of nearly three million in 2016, the state is increasingly dependent on migrant workers from the rest of India, the volume of which appears to be growing beyond three million. The state has evolved as one of the most prominent destinations for migrant labourers from other states in India (Peter and Narendran,2017).

According to the Indian censuses, internal migration is defined as any movement within the political boundaries of the nation which results in a change of usual place of residence from the past residence or place of birth. Based on this, internal movements within the political frontier of states or nation are classified as intra-district, inter-district and inter-state movement. These three categories of internal movements across and within states are together termed as internal migration. Intra-district migrant is a person who is born outside the place of enumeration but within the district of enumeration, who may otherwise be considered as a short-distance migrant. Inter-district migrant refers to a person who crosses the boundary of the district of enumeration but moves within the state of enumeration. We can define him as a medium-distance migrant. Inter-state migrant refers to a person who moves across the boundary of the state of enumeration but within the national boundary. We can consider them as long-distance migrants. Any of these categories of migrants can be categorized as two types namely in-migrants and out-migrants, within the national boundary constituting the quantum of internal migration. In-migrants at the destination are outmigrants from the origin. According to Census, individuals who cross the boundaries of a region for the purpose of living in at the place of enumeration, is an in-migrant. Out-migrants are defined as those people who leave from their place of origin. (Mishra and Rajan,2018)

Kerala has a long history of in-migration, particularly from the neighboring south Indian states, mainly Tamil Nadu. But in the last one and half decades, this south Indian state has been witnessing a huge flow of unskilled workers from some far-off states in East, North and North-east India. The flow from Tamil Nadu has nearly halted and some of the workers have back to their home state. But the flow from a far-off state maintains to develop. We need to distinguish between long distance inter-state migration in a large country like India from the internal migration within a state in the country or even interstate migration to a neighboring state. The physical, linguistic, cultural and social distance among the states of origin and destination state makes such inter-state equal to global migration. Variations exist between global migration and inter-nation migration in phrases of visa requirements and regulations on mobility imposed in a few international locations. People from West Bengal and Assam need to travel 2500- 3500 kilometers to work in Kerala. This is nearly equal to the gap they should travel to migrate to nations in West Asia. A vital issue for a migrant in Kerala is the linguistic variations. Keralites talk Malayalam, a Dravidian language. The mother tongue of the migrant people- Bengali, Oriya, Hindi or Assamese – a lot of these languages belong to the Indo-Aryan language family. Due to language obstacles the migrant workers face problem in having access to training and health care. (Kumar,2017)

A. AN OVERVIEW OF INTERNAL MIGRATION IN INDIA

The magnitude of internal migration is far greater than the international migration in a labor-intensive country like India, where there is enormous human capital contributing abundantly for economic prosperity, social cohesion and cultural diversity. Our country being the seventh largest of the world in geographical terms and second largest in terms of population is been the major contributor of human capital across the world. But the abundant labor population of the country is unevenly distributed resulting scarcity and abundance across different areas which are to an extent corrected through the process of migration. In order to correct the problem of unemployment and labor shortage this migratory flow have to be promoted to the maximum enabling economic development, social welfare and urban-rural diversification. Even though the migration process seems to be inevitable as well as essential component for the overall survival, absence of coherent policy frameworks and strategies adopted for migration makes it not fruitful for both origin and destination. Heavy cost incurred in the human development caused by poor labor arrangements and working conditions, obstacles faced during migration, the problems of food, education and health care facilities transfer the migration process to curse than praise. Further worsen the demography as well as the healthy habitat of the destination.

B. TRENDS OF MIGRATION

On examining the migration trend of Kerala, Kerala is now in a threshold of transition and the consequences of large-scale internal migration to the state which play an important role in framing states future. In the past decades there have been a remarkable flow of labors from other states to Kerala. The economic and social imbalances among the states in India is cause for this huge internal migration in general. Increasing literacy rate by better educational sector and deficiency of unskilled job force and International migration to Gulf and European countries created a huge gap in the Kerala's unskilled labor market even though the state is one with high unemployment rate (educated unemployment 7%) in the country. Along with this the decreasing population growth rate further intensified the situation. Ageing population combined with youth migration to abroad bound to increase labor shortage. The linguistic, social and cultural differences between the state of origin and Kerala and the large distance the migrants have to travel to reach Kerala makes the inter-state migration more similar to International migration. The geographical differences between states in India particularly between North, North east and south India is comparable to different countries in Asia. Moreover, in many cases the distance for inter migration is larger than the crossing of 3 international borders. Kerala is located far off from North, North-East India, the distance to Kochi in Kerala to Kolkata in West Bengal is about 2360km people from Assam have to travel about 3500km to reach Kerala, which is similar to the distance Keralites clear to migrate to Dubai or Abu Dhabi in West Asia.

The differentials in wage rate, Kerala received attention of workers in other states. Migration of workers seeking employment in Kerala from other States like West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa etc. Apart from these workers from neighboring state like Tamil Nadu is increasing but are not paid up to the domestic workers of the state. The contract system of employment is also increasing in the state and they began to move into Kerala and to take work, especially in the construction sectors. What started as trickle soon assumed the dimension of a torrent in the course of a few years. Thus, started the era of replacement of migration to Kerala. (Economic Review.2016) High minimum wage along with improved living condition in Kerala is the main motivating factor for other state workers, the wages are often double or even more than three or four times higher than their home states. For any unskilled work in Kerala the average wage is Rs.500 per day were the national average seems to Rs. 187. In the states like West Bengal, Bihar, Assam and Orissa are provided even lower than the national average. Being the highest wage provider of the country, Kerala is called as 'Gulf of other state migrants' as Gulf was Once and still place of fortune for Keralites. Apart from all these reasons the wage differences between domestic and migrant labors have become an attracting force for the local residents to hire migrant labors for the households rather than domestic workers paved way for the emergence of 'daily wage labor market.'

A Report Commissioned by GIFT (Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation) under Kerala state Finance Department in 2013 submitted to Labor and Rehabilitation Department Government of Kerala says that there more than one million DML (Domestic Migrant Labors) in Kerala across different sectors annually remitting 17,500 crore rupees which is equivalent to 4% of Kerala GDP. It is estimated that 2.35 lakh non-Keralites arrive in Kerala every year. Currently the number estimated in total is 25 lakhs in an age proportion 18-35, with an average wage from 300-500 daily. With the sign of rapid growth of Kerala economy and the increased activities particularly infrastructure and construction sector the in-migration is expected to grow faster in coming years. Apart from its importance in the economic development of the state, interstate migration flow facilitates retaining the demographic balance in a state which has the highest proportion of the aged population and were a good proportion of the population in working age group have migrated out of the state. ‘of migrant labors.

C. WAGE STRUCTURE

The unskilled migrant employees from totally different states in Kerala are for the most part from the agricultural areas. They were forced to migrate as a result of the dearth of job opportunities and low wages in their villages. They were drawn to Kerala as a result of high wages and opportunities to year-around employment in non-agriculture sectors. Wages in Kerala are the highest among all the states in India.

According to the NSSO Employment and state Survey conducted in 2011-12, the standard wage rate of male casual employees among the rural areas was solely Rs. 124 in West Bengal and Odisha and Rs. 143 in Assam. The wage rate in Kerala at Rs. 336 is significantly above not solely the states of origin however conjointly the potential destinations. In fact, the migrants in Kerala are getting rather more than this currently on a daily basis. They are getting as regards to Rs 500 per day.

A vital policy response to cut back migration from rural areas in India was the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS), the work guarantee scheme initiated by the Union Govt. However, when the distinction among the wage rates between states is very high, it becomes nearly robust to arrest the flow of individuals from one region to a different. Moreover, the MGNREGS guarantees employment just for 100 days a year whereas migrant employees in Kerala can get job for 250-300 days. Therefore, the MGNREGS is unlikely to have major influence on the migration from one state to a different if the distinction among the convenience of job opportunities and therefore the wage rates are significantly high.

D. CAUSES OF INTERNAL MIGRATION

India’s population as recorded in census 2011, stands at 1.21 billion. States like Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat and Maharashtra are declared to be economically forward. There are states which could be lacking assets. that is the primary part that contributes to internal migration. Urbanization is one in all the key “pull thing” behind migration today (Deepika and Savadatti 2018). There are many reasons of migration from rural to urban facilities and from vice versa or from one location to another.

Main reasons among of those are:

- Age structural transition
- Changes in the labour market due to expansion of emigration and immigrations of manual workers to the state
- The number of emigrants from Kerala has been increasing year after year. The emigration of Keralites and remittances flowing towards state prompted ‘consumption boom’ which led to increasing construction activities and demand for manual workers in the state
- Continuous outflow of skilled and unskilled labourers created a scarcity of labourers and boosted the wage rate
- Social conflicts and social tensions.
- Gap in civilizations and culture.

- Law and order situation.
- Inequalities within the obtainable social and economic opportunities and alternative amenities of life between groups of people and or sectors.
- Income maximization
- Inequitable distribution of benefits of economic development.
- Social mobility and status of aspirations.
- Need for attaining lifestyle, performance and enjoyment.

E. RESEARCH GAP

Basically, all the studies on migration are focusing on International Migration. But few studies have centered on internal migration and domestic migrant labors. The issues like the sectors employed, the nature of employment, Wages provided etc. are necessary aspects which require more examination. Research in Kerala migration have been widely studied based on flow of remittance, the social and demography to an extent of both origin and destination. several migration analysts have given factual description and theoretical aspects of migration however of these studies have confined in International migration mainly. Most of the researchers have shown lesser interest in internal migration studies as a result of the shortage of accessibility of actual data sources and therefore the difficulties incurred in assortment of information on comparing with International migration studies.

F. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the patterns of migration to Kerala?
- What are the important determinants determining the large-scale migration?
- What are the changes viewed socially and economically in Kerala?
- What is the wage difference existing between migrant and domestic workers?

G. OBJECTIVES

- To study the socio-economic conditions of the migrant workers in Kerala;
- To study the wage and employment pattern among the migrants in Kerala;
- To identify welfare and social security provisions for migrant workers;

H. CHAPTER SCHEME

The first chapter is the Introduction section giving a general profile of internal migration, India and Kerala in specific, followed by the research gap of the study, research questions, and objectives. The second chapter Titles literature reviews. The third chapter titled data and methodology gives the detailed profile of the selected district and the methodology. The fourth chapter has the result and discussion part which is broadly divided into 5 sections namely; profile of the worker, process of migration, living conditions, wages and savings, and health and security. The final Chapter titled Findings and conclusion comprises the major findings of the study followed by suggestions and conclusion.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There are number of studies pertaining the topic migration resulting to the flow of remittance and thereby implications in both origin and destination. On discussing on migration, we generally discuss on International migration which have brought about a drastic change in Country as the largest remittance receiving nation and Kerala being placed at the top among the state with 40%. Many studies have been conducted in this regard especially to Gulf countries. But the studies on internal migration from Kerala and to Kerala are few. In this part, review of literatures includes various studies related to internal migration in India in general and Kerala in Specific, related to Social, Economic and cultural implications. Initially analyzing the concept of migration and its trend in general, then nationally and then focusing on different dimensions of internal migration.

Roy and Nijim (1991) This is an exploratory study made on the basis of migration data of 2 censuses of 1971 and 1981. It tries to match a number of the vital variables of quality in terms of (place of birth) and POLR (place of last residence) that have reacted into the modification of usual residence of individuals inflicting thereby shift of population. the topic being advanced and large, it's going to be troublesome to project all potential things at one place. However, the readers might attempt to check a number of the findings additional profitably by field orientated investigations specially resulting in establish varied social-economic fall outs. Migration study is processional within the analysis of population issues that has collapsible into its orbit, in real sense of the term -idealized migration policies. within the country, like ours, it's essential to actually spell out some policy to visualize urban swelling of population and to strengthen the agricultural area to cut back regional imbalances at the individual level so real development is achieved. a number of these queries on migration are exhibit during this paper to take up additional to promote policy formations and to organize the migrant work force for an improved India.

Krishnan (1991) examines the wage structure and wage movements and their relation employment and output in the agrarian economy. It developed a concept of interrelated labor market where it is divided into four sections, relation with agriculture-construction sector, rural urban transition but estimating vector auto regressions and testing the casual relationship among the different wage rates. The paper also emphasis on the importance of social norms in labor market behavior, movements in the wage relatives in relation to the changes in the produce demand and also develop an analytical model to explain employment behavior in interrelated labor market to explain the changes in the output and employment in the agrarian sector of Kerala economy.

Gosh and Sharma (1995) emphasizes on the migration pattern on rural Bihar. In this paper a survey results of 56 sample villages spread over six districts have mentions that there is lowest incidence migration in better agriculture areas and highest incidence of migration in better agriculture areas and highest incidence of migration in the opposite environment. They migrate to Punjab, West Bengal, Delhi, Assam and Kerala for their job. Temporary migrants out migrate for a particular or specified period. The author also points out the destination and the occupation of migrant workers. Migration of workers generally takes place from areas of low employment to those with high employment. Kerala had too witnessed a large number of migrant workers from Bihar just before the advent of the migrant workers from the north eastern states. The study mainly focuses on the pattern of the aspects of rural migration.

Pillai (1996) In recent years the Kerala government has initiated several measures to provide social security to workers in a wide range of activities in the unorganized sector. Welfare funds have been created and are administered by tripartite statutory welfare boards. This article examines the functioning of one of the oldest fund schemes, the Kerala Headload Workers Welfare Scheme.

Ravi and Sasikumar (2003) deals with both international and internal migration which have a large-scale impact on economic growth and reduction in scale of poverty in many parts of India. The paper recommends for changes in government policies with proper improvement in international and internal migration policies and laws. And in the case of International migration they suggest for the maximization of the emigrational tendencies with appropriate institutional and policy measures. They advocated the policies by dividing their suggestions under four categories like improving the synergy between migration and development secondly improving labor market outcomes, thirdly ensuring of basic entitlements to migrant workers and finally improving the social and political environment for migration.

Grimm (2005) pointed out that the migrant workers come to sell his labor power where there is a labor shortage. They admitted to do certain kind of Job. They had no rights, claims or reality outside his filling of the job. While he fills it, they paid and accommodated. It is not men who immigrate but machine minders, sweepers, cement mixers, cleaners etc. This is significance to temporary migration

Skeldon (2008) emphasis on migration and development. The paper reviews the minority of migrants, the flow of remittance, the problem of skilled labor (brain drain) and the migration diaspora. It explains on how the current trends and concerns over migration and development with a traditional focus on emigrational studies, its cause and effects on movement of people and the policy designs to protect and promote migrants to inhibit development. The paper put forward the need for research on integration of urbanization, international migration and development and also the reaction of a new socio- economic and political space. And the need for the framing of laws and policies for migrants which have become an integral part of development.

Keshri and Bhagat. (2010). Conceptual Several family unit level investigations have recorded across the board transitory and occasional movement in various parts of India, yet there has been a deficiency of data on the size and attributes of brief and regular relocation at the state and national levels. This is fundamentally in light of the fact that the evaluation does not give data on transitory and regular movement and the National Sample Survey has not gathered brief relocation information until 1999-2000. In this investigation, we break down the unit level information on transitory and occasional relocation from the 1999-2000 National Sample Survey to comprehend the power and provincial/state insightful variety, country urban differentials of impermanent and regular movement, and their relationship with neediness and absence of education. The examination demonstrates that transitory and regular movement is more predominant in rustic than urban zones. We additionally locate that poor, especially socially in reverse gatherings known as Scheduled Tribes in India have a higher penchant to move incidentally. Transitory and regular relocation has a critical and positive relationship with destitution and absence of education in provincial territories, yet in urban regions happier families are more inclined to move. The discoveries recommend that brief and occasional movement in country India is basically trouble driven and dominantly among planned clans, unskilled people and the poorest of poor people.

Kumar (2011) examines the dimension of vulnerability of other state migrant laborers in the sub-national context taking Kerala as the area of study. Analyzing how the host (Kerala) respond to reduce the vulnerability if interstate migrant laborers and also to make an assessment of a pioneering welfare scheme for the migrant workers, which are introduced by Government of Kerala. The paper points on the portability of entitlements are the lack of rights which they enjoyed before migration and how the state and the Central government have to call for a better coordination among both the origin and destination. It also calls for the strategy to unify the migrants providing and making aware about their rights where the authorities fails to reach to significant segment of migrant population. The study has been conducted through primary data collection technique from migrant workers, state officials, employers/agents/contractors. The paper concludes suggesting for a multi-institutional and multidimensional comprehensive study on the migrant workers population which is a major component of Kerala's employment sector.

Kundu and Sarswati (2012) deal on the migration and urbanization patters in recent decades. The study analyzes the trend and pattern of migration in Indian using the population census data (1961-2011) and NSS data (1983-2008), carried out in national and state level focusing on the trends and patterns of internal migration, gender and geographical boundaries of movements separately from rural to urban areas. Along with that changing pattern of mobility of migrant workers, Employment structure of migrant adult their social economic characteristics and the overview on urbanization trending the macro level.

Czaika (2012) analyze the multiple dimensions and factors in internal and international migration, focusing on pattern of migration by analyzing the role of households, capabilities and aspirations of migrants, risk involved and the in temporal income and consumption relative to deprivation. According the study it is revealed that the rural migration is higher than the urban migration and an intra-state migration is increasing over the past years.

Upadhya and Rutten (2012) the paper reviews migration and development, by debating the current flows and reverse flow of migrant resources to India, giving a clear-cut understanding of migration and migrants socio-economic implications. The paper is detail discussion in transactional mobility and the development achieved thereby. The study put forward a methodological approach to the flow and reverse flow involved in migration providing an organizational structure, in transactional social fields regulating the flow of migration, which will help to provide a comprehensive understanding of migration and development.

Rajanand Moses (2012) on their study on labor migration and integration in Kerala, tried to show out of state migrants are kept isolated from the surrounding community. From the study it is found that migrant workers to Kerala are unable to integrate with the local workers and community and have no information about the prevailing local wage, their rights, working hours and the amenities provided in the work sites. They opine that the labor union have to be effective and keen in integrating the workers and the locals in Kerala so that their working environment will be safe and secure.

Jayarajan (2013) attempts to solve the research gap on family migration in India were the 'push- pull factors' in family migration by identifying strands of reasons with hypothetical examples. The family migration is discussed by incorporating the complex interplays in it. Besides that, the social, Political, development and environmental factors for a comprehensive understanding is done. Emigrational trends are considered in connection with the growth theory and third world urbanization the major factors leading to the spatial mobility of families in India were the number of migrants increased from 1.7 lakhs in 1993 to 3.5 lakhs in 2007-08 s per the study.

Narayana and Venkiteswaran (2013) domestic migrant labor in Kerala are estimated the stock and flows of migrant labors. Even though the unemployment rate hit by 7.4% Kerala is home for 25 lakh migrant workers. The socio-economic characteristics, working and living conditions of migrant workers are studied. As per the study Perumbavoor, a place in Ernakulam 12 district of Kerala has a greater number of migrant workers in Kerala. As per the studies conducted over there, they have made recommendations that they must be provided a unique registration id card and it can be used for availing benefits of all the schemes that the different departments of the state government offer to the domestic migrant laborers. It is suggested that the provision of affordable housing and associated services to migrant workers may be done by the state government through the formation of non-profit organization under section 25 of the Companies Act. They also suggested that the states government undertake awareness programmes among the migrant workers and the employers employing them.

John (2014) points out that seasonal migration has been a source of income for rural households who are unable to support themselves and the family through agriculture. Household's number diversify their (the migrant worker's) economic activities outside the traditional agriculture sphere to urban areas in the lean period. He points to different demographic and socio-economic factors such as age sex, educational qualification, religion etc. as some causes leading to this temporary migration.

Ahmad (2014) deals with the emerging trends in the Indian economy with the inflow of remittance and the related phenomena. The Journal gives an approximate estimation on the countries from which India receives the highest remittance as the top position is for North America followed by Europe and Middle East countries. Whole is divided mainly as three parts as the role of remittance in overall development with special focus on merits of remittances received in the Indian economy, secondly the different phases of migration and finally the domination of Gulf countries in remittance proportion. The journal in detail discussed the flow and role of remittance in and to different sectors but need not discussed the major utilizers of this remittance and confined it to a statement as macro and micro development rather than specifying it.

P.K. and Viswanath (2015) the paper makes an empirical enquiry on the socio-economic conditions of unorganized sector domestic migrant labors (DML) OF Ernakulam district in the central part of Kerala and suggest the strategies for improving the working and living conditions of the migrant laborers of the state.

Puthuma (2016) the paper observes the extent of native labor availability in the rural labor market and also to analyses the scope of migrant workers in the current labor market through the secondary data sources, from the three sectors namely agriculture, industrial and service sector. The coming of migrant labors is magnified as a relief for the deficit in the manual labor market of the state as they supply cheap labor force in the labor market. The paper observes decreased gap between the demand and supply of labor especially on agriculture sector, were the sector presently exist because of the availability of migrant labors.

Anju (2016) the paper studies the various aspects of inter-state migration in Kerala, by analyzing the existence of high wage and lack of domestic manual labor resulting to a high inflow of migrant workers from different parts of the country. By tracing their social and economic characteristics and also by identifying the factors that determine the standard of living of migrant labors in Kerala, using the linear regression model to determine the standard of living.

CHAPTER 3

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

A. DISTRICT PROFILE OF CALICUT

Kozhikode district is situated on the south west coast of India. The district is bounded on the north by Kannur district, on the east by Wayanad district, on the south by Malappuram district and on the west by the Arabian Sea. Topographically the district has three distinct regions - the sandy, the rocky highlands formed by the hilly portion of the Western Ghats and lateritic midland. Of the total area of 2344 sq.kms., the sandy coastal belt is 362.85 sq.kms., lateritic midlands 1343.50 sq.kms. And rocky highlands 637.65 sq.kms. All the three taluks are spread over the three regions. The district has a coastal length of about 80 kms. The highland region accounts for 26.80 per cent and the lowland region for 15.55 per cent of the total area of the district. The Kozhikode district came into existence on 1st January 1957, originally consisting of five taluks, Vadakara, Koyilandy, Kozhikode, Ernad&Tirur. With the formation of Malappuram district on 1st June 1969 & Wayanad on 1st November 1980, Kozhikode district now consist of one revenue division, three taluks, twelve blocks, 78 panchayats and 117 villages.

B. THE METHODOLOGY OF PRIMARY SURVEY

The data have been collected from the primary sources. But to cover the objectives in specific the study intends to use primary data collected through a pre-tested semi-structured schedule extensively. The data has been collected from different parts of Calicut dividing as North, Centre and South interviewing both migrant and domestic labors from low skilled sector. Which would be helpful to know the real essence of huge labor migration from different parts of the country to Calicut district of Kerala covering most of the area under production and service sector where the migrant unskilled labor force is dominant.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MIGRATION PATTERN

On discussing on any migration trends there will be different push and pull factors. In Kerala the push factors like poverty, population density, unemployment, agricultural failure or low yield, low demand for domestic laborers, low wages, disasters, religious and caste issues. Along with it the pull factors like high wages, better employment opportunities, improved living conditions, free health and education factors etc. play the role. In this section of the chapter the various factors determine the migration trends of the labor workers in Calicut district of Kerala was been analyzed.

A. RELEGION OF THE MIGRANT LABOURS

From the below shown Table 1, it is observed that among the different religious migrants' community from other states of India it is the Muslim community dominates with 51.43% followed by Hindu community 47.14% and nominal of 1.43% of Christian community.

Religion	Number	Percentage
Hindu	33	47.14
Muslim	36	51.43
Christian	1	1.43
Total	70	100

Table 1: Distribution of Migrant labour by religion

Source: Primary survey

B. CASTE OF THE MIGRANT LABOURS

From the below shown Table 2, it is evident that OBC (55.71%) is the largest caste followed by ST (24.29%). The SC is of very nominal in number with 20% out of the total of 70 migrant samples selected.

Caste	Number	Percentage
ST	17	24.29
SC	14	20
OBC	39	55.71
Total	70	100

Table 2: Distribution of Migrant labors by caste

Source: Primary survey

C. DOMICILE OF MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 3 shows the percentage of labor migrant flow from other states of India. As per the survey Uttarakhand have the highest number of migrants with 51.43% followed by Jharkhand 25.71% and Rajasthan 20%. Uttar Pradesh with least of 2.86% in the migrant labor flow. UP people are engaged in furniture manufacturing and rest are scattered among different semi-skilled sectors of the state. Presently the other state workers are engaged even in the plantation, traditional agricultural cultivation and construction due to scarcity of domestic labors.

Domicile	Number	Percentage
Rajasthan	14	20
Jharkhand	18	25.71
Uttarakhand	36	51.43
Uttar Pradesh	2	2.86
Total	70	100

Table 3: Distribution of Migrant labors by domicile

Source: Primary survey

D. NATURE OF EMPLOYMENT

The Table 4 shows the different sectors or nature of the employment in which migrant labors are engaged. More than half say 51.43% of the workers are engaged in daily wage jobs. It clearly defines the emerging 'migrant daily labor market in Kerala'. 47.14% are engaged in contract jobs, in the initial stages of the migrant labor flow it was through the contractors and agents the labors are been taken from different parts of the country. Very nominal number of 1.43% are engaged in permanent jobs and other related works. Due to mobile characteristics of the migrant workers everywhere they are employed and paid in daily basis. The majority of the migrant labors are illiterate rural population who become the mere preys of exploitation by the contractors and the domestic population. They are hired and employed without following the labor laws and regulations like police station registration, special ID cards, the record of their personnel details and Insurance facilities.

Nature of Employment	Number	Percentage
Daily wage	36	51.43
Contract	33	47.14
Others	1	1.43
Total	70	100

Table 4: Distribution of Migrant labors by nature of employment

Source: Primary survey

E. LEVEL OF EDUCATION

From the Table 5 it is clear that more than half of the migrant population say 61.43 % of the people have education up to secondary level followed by a 12.86% of migrant people are having primary education and 25.71% people who are illiterate. During the survey it is observed that people from Jharkhand and Uttarakhand are more illiterate and primarily educated but states like Rajasthan Uttar Pradesh have an educational qualification up to secondary level. From this it can be concluded that the increase in the literacy rate of the Kerala have created a wide employment gap in the low skilled sectors of the Kerala economy.

Level of Education	Number	Percentage
Illiterate	18	25.71
Primary	9	12.86
Secondary	43	61.43
Total	70	100

Table 5: Distribution of Migrant labors by level of education

Source: Primary survey

F. MARITAL STATUS

From Table 6 it is observed that about 57.14% of the migrant population are unmarried youth, followed by 42.86% of married. From the survey it is observed that about 99 % of the migrant workers are men and that to under the age of 30. Only very few migrants take their family along with them, as their wife's working along with them or as maids in Kerala, with their children accommodated in the Government schools.

Marital Status	Number	Percentage
Married	30	42.86
Not married	40	57.14
Total	70	100

Table 6: Distribution of Migrant labors by marital status

Source: Primary survey

G. AGE OF THE MIGRANT LABOURERS

The Table 7 shows the age categories of the migrant workers to Kerala from other states 8.57% of the workers are in the age category of below 20 followed by 72.86% in the age group of 20-30 and 14.29% in the age group of 30-40. Only 4.29% are between the age category of 40-50 and above. This shows that the migrant labors are a very young working force.

Age	Number	Percentage
Below 20	6	8.57
20-30	51	72.86
30-40	10	14.29
40-50	3	4.29
Total	70	100

Table 7: Distribution of Migrant labors by age

Source: Primary survey

H. ACCOMMODATION OF THE MIGRANT LABOURERS

From the Survey it is viewed that the labors from other parts of the country have poor accommodation facilities. As per the labor laws and norms it is the duty of the employer to provide good accommodation facilities to the workers but the facilities provided to them are not satisfactory. It is observed that people live in cemented, others in pukka houses. Most of them living in fully furnished or pukka houses are rented by the workers (74.29%) itself rather than depending on the employer. The contract labors working in the construction sites live in the construction sites or in rented houses where rent paid by the employer itself (25.71%).

Accommodation	Number	Percentage
Rented House	52	74.29
House rent paid by the employer	18	25.71
Total	70	100

Table 8: Distribution of Migrant labors by accommodation

Source: Primary survey

I. INCOME OF THE MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 9 shows the income of the migrant labourers. From the data it is observed that about 25.71% of the migrant labors are getting an income which is below 10000 followed by 1.43% get an income in between 10000-20000 and the majority from the total sample of 70 get an income more than 20000 which accounts for 72.86%.

Income of labourers	Number	Percentage
Below 10000	18	25.71
10000-20000	1	1.43
20000-30000	51	72.86
Total	70	100

Table 9: Distribution of Migrant labors by income of labourers

Source: Primary survey

J. HOME VISIT OF THE MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 10 below shows the type of home visit preferred by the migrant labourers. It is clear that only a few percentages that is 1.43% use to visit the home once in a year, and the majority of the total sample selected for the survey (98.57%) visits their home during the festivals.

Home Visit	Number	Percentage
Once in a year	1	1.43
During festivals	69	98.57
Total	70	100

Table 10: Distribution of Migrant labors by home visit

Source: Primary survey

K. WORKING TIME OF MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 11 shows the total working hours of the migrant workers. In this more than half of the labourers (72.86%) work for 8hrs followed by 7-8hrs working time it consists of a percentage of 25.71% and only 1.43% works for 6-7hrs.

Working Time (hours)	Number	Percentage
6-7	1	1.43
7-8	18	25.71
8	51	72.86
Total	70	100

Table 11: Distribution of Migrant labors by working time

Source: Primary survey

L. TRAINING ATTAINED BY THE MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 12 shown below represents the training attained by the migrant labors. From the survey it is clear that those workers who are experienced consists of 21.43% and the majority of 78.57% are pursuing on the job training.

Training Attained	Number	Percentage
Experienced	15	21.43
On the job training	55	78.57
Total	70	100

Table 12: Distribution of Migrant labors by training attained

Source: Primary survey

M. TIME TAKEN TO ACQUIRE SKILLS BY MIGRANT LABOURERS

The Table 13 shows the results of the time taken by the migrant labourers in acquiring the skills. About 52.86% of them take a period of 1 year for acquiring the skills followed by 25.71% who takes a time span of 6 months and the remaining 21.43% are experience labourers.

Time Taken to Acquire Skills	Number	Percentage
1 Year	37	52.86
6 Months	18	25.71
Nil	15	21.43
Total	70	100

Table 13: Distribution of Migrant labors by time taken to acquire skills

Source: Primary survey

N. PURPOSE OF LOAN TAKEN FROM EMPLOYER BY THE MIGRANT LABOURERS

The purpose of taking loan from the employer consists of various reasons which include illness at home (44.29%), repayment of loan (48.57%), children's education (4.29%) and other matters of concern (2.86%) out of the 70 samples collected from the Calicut district of Kerala.

Purpose of Loan	Number	Percentage
Illness at home	31	44.29
Repayment of loan	34	48.57
Children's education	3	4.29
Others	2	2.86
Total	70	100

Table 14: Distribution of Migrant laborers by purpose of loan

Source: Primary survey

O. PAYMENT OF WAGES TO MIGRANT LABOURS

From the Table 15 it is clear that the majority of the migrant labors are paid for overtime and also wages are given on time, but other than wages they don't get any allowances in form of money. If in case of emergency such as illness in home, repayment of loan, or for the education of their children they are provided loan by the employer in most cases. Workers have a provision for sick leave but there is no such option for paid leave. Migrant labors remit the wages they earned, to home by bank.

Particulars	YES	NO
Paid for overtime	69	1
Timely payment	70	0
Other allowances	0	70
Loan from the employer	69	1
Sick leave	69	1
Paid leave	0	70
Remittance of money	70	0

Table 15: Payment of Wages to Migrant Labourers

Source: Primary survey

P. WORKING DAYS OF MIGRANT LABOURS

The Table 16 shows the total number of working days in a year. More number of workers are engaged in job for 250-300 days (72.86%) followed by 200-250 working days, it consists of a percentage of 25.71% and a very less number are engaged in working for more than 300 days that include a percentage of 1.43%.

Working Days	Number	Percentage
200-250	18	25.71
250-300	51	72.86
Above 300	1	1.43
Total	70	100

Table 16: Distribution of Migrant laborers by working days

Source: Primary survey

Q. HEALTH OF MIGRANT LABOURERS

Even though the migrant workers have no health insurance they are provided with high class health facilities. They are given proper treatment in hospitals, as they got the priority in there, and also while doing hazardous jobs proper measures are taken for their protection. Hence looking towards their health facilities, it is all-round good.

Particulars	Yes	No
Protection from hazardous substances	70	0
Treatment	70	0
Health Insurance	0	70
Employer payment for medicine	0	70

Table 17: Health Status of Migrant Labourers

Source: Primary survey

R. COMMUNICATION WITH LOCALS BY THE MIGRANT LABOURS

From Table 18 it is observed that a majority of labourers, say 68.57% are having very less communication with locals followed by 25.71%, they have no communication and only a few percentages of 5.71% has learned the local language for the purpose of communication.

Communication with Locals	Number	Percentage
Has learned the local language	4	5.71
Very less communication	48	68.57
No communication	18	25.71
Total	70	100

Table 18: Distribution of Migrant labors by communication with locals

Source: Primary survey

S. SOCIAL SECURITY OF THE MIGRANT LABOURS

The migrant labors from different states of India usually opt for living in group, they lead a different life as compared with the local native workers so that local labor unions don't approach them. They are properly treated and they use to attend all the social functions happening near to them. They all are owning ration cards, majority of them belongs to BPL category and having voters' card.

Particulars	Yes	No
Participation in social functions	70	0
Approach of local unions	0	70
Aware of any collective organization	0	70
Ration card	70	0
APL	2	68
Voter's card	61	9

Table 19: Social Security Status of Migrant Labourers

Source: Primary survey

CHAPTE 5

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

A. FINDINGS

This section of the report consists the major findings which have come up from the study, and various suggestions based on the findings and a conclusion on the internal migration to Calicut city of Kerala its trends, patterns and nature.

The major findings of the study are:

- The migrant labor community comprise a major proportion of male population with 57.14% of unmarried men within an age group of 20-30 years (72.86%) followed by 30-40 years (14.29%) from (Table 6) and (Table 7).
- 51.43% of the migrant population are Muslims mainly from Uttarakhand 47.14% of Hindu a mixed population from the states like Rajasthan, Jharkhand and Uttar Pradesh followed by 1.43% of Christians who are from Jharkhand.
- In the case of accommodation, about 74.29% of labors have rented house and the remaining workers house rent is paid by the employer (25.71%) (Table 8) shows it.
- The educational level of Migrant labors are satisfactory,61.43% have secondary education followed by12.86% labors attained primary education. Remaining 25.71% are illiterate, they are from the state of Jharkhand (Table 5).
- Uttarakhand is the state with highest migrant population (51.43%) followed by Jharkhand (25.71%) Rajasthan being the third (20%) and Uttar Pradesh is with the least population of 2.86% from (Table 3).
- Most of the migrant labors are working as daily labors (51.43%) and other on contract basis (47.14%) from (Table 4).
- On analyzing the remittance details all of the migrant labors remit money to their home state through banks which is been accounted properly. (Table 15).
- Most of the migrant labors are not experienced, they get on the job training (78.57%) (Table 12) and in most cases they take at least 1 year in acquiring skills (Table 13).Usually they work for 8 hours per day (72.86%)and they are earning a wage of 20000-30000 per month (72.86) (Table 11 and Table 9).
- Migrant workers are getting proper treatment in hospitals and they are also provided with proper safety measures while doing hazardous jobs but they are lacking health insurance (Table 17).
- Majority of the migrant labors are having very less communication (68.57%) with the locals (Table 18). So, they are not aware of any collective organizations and local unions never approaches them also due to lack of contact. But they used to attend every social function (Table 19).

B. SUGGESTIONS

From the results and findings emerged from the study, there is clearly a need to address the following problems to have a healthy and useful contribution by this migratory process:

- A compulsory registration of migrant labors to account the correct flow of migration including the personal and migratory details.
- Improving the housing and living conditions of the labors. The government officials should ensure that adequate facilities are provided by the employer or companies who hire the labors.
- Adoption of Social security measure like insurance, health cards, work card etc. and other credentials, which includes judicial services too.
- Establishing help centers similar to foreign embassies for international migrants to solve their problems on social, living and employment related issues.
- Measures to sustain good relation with the native population by migrant people as presently they being treated as a secondary citizen.

- Ensuring every migrant worker hired have Bank A/C, so that exact accounting of wage, remittance and money flow from the Kerala economy can be accounted.

C. CONCLUSION

Even though all these issues and problems were faced by them, most of them still wish to stay in Kerala as it is the place of virtue for them. Where they could earn more money, have good climate and good food. Even many commands that the Malayali community is good and behave gently compared to the landlords and Zamindars of their region. Along with this there exist a specified community who oppose this huge labor migration to Kerala by accusing them as the carriers of infectious diseases, unhygienic community and reasons for the emergence of slums in Kerala. Many in turn accuse them for the increasing crimes in the state. But on examining the growth of Kerala GDP and the contribution of this in-migrant laborers in the growth of each sector especially in the unskilled labor sector where the state had faced huge crisis over the past years is indispensable as now even the agriculture had also started in demanding them with the increasing shortage of labor for work. The large-scale migration from all parts of the country to Kerala holds a true story of migrant's flows, a scrip replete opportunity, exploitations, sacrifices, gains and hopes. A perfect plot of other state peoples who build up their edifices by the lives, contributions and atrocities of migrant laborers. While Kerala has the same replica treading its path called development in the cost of thousands of lives and their emotions, with a bad side of cultural divide. A state with better human indices and sensibilities. Migrant laborers in the state are not enjoying any protection under the labor laws of the central as well as the state. No appropriate welfare measures and to a minimum social security floor. One of the main constraints the state face on the large-scale labor migration is framing policies for the migrant workers and their socio-economic concerns, due to the absence of authentic information and data on the existing and flowing migrant workers in the state. The people from different states with distinct culture and food habit migrated with same motive. It would not be sufficient to think of migrant laborers as a single set without differing backgrounds and needs and a culturally sensitive intervention would be effective in understanding and formulating effective and necessary steps to maintain a healthy flow of migrant laborers to the state which is now a necessity to sustain Kerala's economic growth.

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